

Double Reverse θ^* - Centralizer of Rings With Involution

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Abstract.

Let R be a ring with involution and θ is a mapping of R . It was known that every double reverse θ^* -centralizer is a double Jordan θ^* -centralizer on R but the converse need not be true. In this paper we give conditions to the converse to be true.

Keywords:

*- Ring; semiprime *- ring; reverse *- centralizer; involution; double reverse θ^* - centralizer; double Jordan θ^* - centralizer.

1. Introduction

Let R be a ring with involution and θ is a mapping of R . This paper consists of two sections. In section one, we recall some basic definitions and other concepts, which be used in our paper, we explain these concepts by examples and remarks. In section two, we introduce the concepts of double reverse θ^* - centralizer, double Jordan θ^* - centralizer and we study the relation between them on R .

2. BASIC CONCEPTS

Definition 2.1: [1] A ring R is called a prime ring if for any $a, b \in R$, $aRb = \{0\}$, implies that either $a = 0$ or $b = 0$.

Definition 2.2: [1] A ring R is called a semiprime ring if for any $a \in R$, $aRa = \{0\}$, implies that $a = 0$.

Remark 2.3 : [1] Every prime ring is a semiprime ring, but the converse in general is not true.

Example 2.4: [1] Let $R = Z_6$ be a ring. To show that the ring R is semiprime ring, let $a \in R$ such that $aRa = 0$, implies that $a^2 = 0$, hence $a = 0$, therefore R is semiprime ring. But R is not prime since $2 \neq 0$ and $3 \neq 0$, implies that $2R3 = 0$.

Definition 2.5 :[1] A ring R is said to be n - torsion free where $n \neq 0$ is an integer if whenever $na = 0$ with $a \in R$, then $a = 0$

Definition 2.6 :[2] An additive mapping $x \rightarrow x^*$ on a ring R is called an involution if for all $x, y \in R$ we have $(xy)^* = y^* x^*$ and $x^{**} = x$. A ring equipped with an involution is called *- ring.

Definition 2.7:[2] A left (right) reverse $*$ - centralizer of $*$ - ring R is an additive mapping $T: R \rightarrow R$ which satisfies $T(xy) = T(y)x^*$ ($T(xy) = y^*T(x)$) for all $x,y \in R$. A reverse $*$ - centralizer of a ring R is both left and right reverse $*$ - centralizer.

Definition 2.8:[2] A left (right) Jordan $*$ - centralizer of $*$ - ring R is an additive mapping $T: R \rightarrow R$ which satisfies $T(x^2) = T(x)x^*$ ($T(x^2) = x^*T(x)$) for all $x \in R$. A Jordan $*$ - centralizer of a ring R is both left and right Jordan $*$ - centralizer.

Remark 2.9 :[3] Every left (right) reverse $*$ - centralizer is a left (right) Jordan $*$ - centralizer, but the converse in general is not true.

Example 2.10:[3] Let F be a field, and R be a ring of triangular matrices of the form

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a & c & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a,b,c,d \in F, x \in R.$$

And the involution $*$ define by

$$* \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & a & c & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a & c & -b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a,b,c \in F.$$

And let $T: R \rightarrow R$ is an additive mapping defined as

$$T(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } b \in F \text{ and } x \in R.$$

Then T is a Jordan $*$ - centralizer but is not reverse $*$ - centralizer.

Theorem 2.11:[4] Let R be a 2-torsion free semiprime $*$ -ring, then every left (right) Jordan $*$ - centralizer is a left (right) reverse $*$ - centralizer.

Definition 2.12:[3] Let R be a $*$ - ring, and $T, S: R \rightarrow R$ be additive mappings, then a pair (T,S) is called a double reverse $*$ - centralizer if T is a left reverse $*$ - centralizer, S is a right reverse $*$ - centralizer, and they satisfying the condition $x^*T(y) = S(x)y^*$, for all $x, y \in R$.

Example 2.13:[3] Let F be a field, and let $M_2(F)$ be a ring of all matrices of order 2 over F , and the involution $*$ on $M_2(F)$ defined by

$$* \left(\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} a & c \\ b & d \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F.$$

Let $T, S: M_2(F) \rightarrow M_2(F)$ be additive mappings defined as

$$T \left(\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ b & d \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F.$$

$$S \left(\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & c \\ 0 & d \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F.$$

Then (T, S) is a double reverse $*$ -centralizer.

Definition 2.14 [3]: Let R be $*$ -ring, and $T, S : R \rightarrow R$ be additive mappings, then a pair (T, S) is called a double Jordan $*$ -centralizer if T is a left Jordan $*$ -centralizer, S is a right Jordan $*$ -centralizer, and they satisfying the condition $x^*T(x) = S(x)x^*$, for all $x \in R$.

Remark 2.15 [3]: Every double reverse $*$ -centralizer is a double Jordan $*$ -centralizer, but the converse in general is not true.

Example 2.16 [3]: Let R and the involution $*$ be as in the Example (2.10), and

$T, S : R \rightarrow R$ be additive mappings defined as

$$T(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } S(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b \in F \text{ and } x \in R.$$

Then (T, S) is a double Jordan $*$ -centralizer, but is not a double reverse $*$ -centralizer.

Definition 2.17[5]: A left (right) reverse θ^* -centralizer of $*$ -ring R is an additive mapping $T : R \rightarrow R$ which satisfies $T(xy) = T(y)\theta(x^*)$ ($T(xy) = \theta(y^*)T(x)$) for all $x, y \in R$, where θ is a mapping of R . A reverse θ^* -centralizer of $*$ -ring R is both left and right θ^* -centralizer.

Definition 2.18[5]: A left (right) Jordan θ^* -centralizer of $*$ -ring R is an additive mapping $T : R \rightarrow R$ which satisfies $T(x^2) = T(x)\theta(x^*)$ ($T(x^2) = \theta(x^*)T(x)$) for all $x \in R$, where θ is a mapping of R . A Jordan θ^* -centralizer of $*$ -ring R is both left and right Jordan θ^* -centralizer.

3. DOUBLE REVERSE θ^* -CENTRALIZER

Definition 3.1: Let R be a $*$ -ring, and $T, S : R \rightarrow R$ be additive mappings, then a pair (T, S) is called a double reverse θ^* -centralizer if T is a left reverse θ^* -centralizer, S is a right reverse θ^* -centralizer, and they satisfying the condition $\theta(x^*)T(y) = S(x)\theta(y^*)$, for all $x, y \in R$, where θ is a mapping of R .

Example 3.2: Let F be a field, and let $M_2(F)$ be a ring of all matrices of order 2 over F , and the involution $*$ on $M_2(F)$ defined by

$$* \left(\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} a & c \\ b & d \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F.$$

Let $T, S : M_2(F) \rightarrow M_2(F)$ be additive mappings defined as

$$T \left(\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ b & d \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F.$$

$$S \left(\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & c \\ 0 & d \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F.$$

And let $\theta : M_2(F) \rightarrow M_2(F)$ defined by

$$\theta \left(\begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F.$$

Then (T, S) is a double reverse θ^* -centralizer.

Definition 3.3: Let R be a $*$ -ring, and $T, S : R \rightarrow R$ be additive mappings, then a pair (T, S) is called a double Jordan θ^* -centralizer if T is a left Jordan θ^* -centralizer, S is a right Jordan θ^* -centralizer, and they satisfying the condition $\theta(x^*)T(x) = S(x)\theta(x^*)$, for all $x \in R$, where θ is a mapping of R .

Remark 3.4: Let R be $*$ -ring and θ is a mapping of R . Every double reverse θ^* -centralizer is a double Jordan θ^* -centralizer, but the converse in general is not true.

Example 3.5: Let F be a field, and R be a ring of triangular matrices of the form.

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a & c & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c, d \in F, x \in R.$$

And the involution $*$ define by

$$* \left(\begin{bmatrix} 0 & a & c & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a & c & -b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c \in F, \text{ and}$$

$T, S : R \rightarrow R$ be additive mappings defined as

$$T(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } S(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b \in F \text{ and } x \in R.$$

And let $\theta: R \rightarrow R$ defined by

$$\theta(x) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & a & c & b \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & c \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ for all } a, b, c \in F \text{ and } x \in R.$$

Then (T, S) is a double Jordan θ^* -centralizer, but is not a double reverse θ^* -centralizer.

The converse of Remark (3.4) is true under certain conditions, as in the following theorems.

Theorem 3.6: Let R be a 2-torsion free semiprime $*$ -ring, then every double Jordan θ^* -centralizer is a double reverse θ^* -centralizer, where θ is an automorphism of R .

Proof: Using Theorem (2.11), we have T is a left reverse θ^* -centralizer, S is a right reverse θ^* -centralizer. We are done if we can show that $\theta(x^*)T(y) = S(x)\theta(y^*)$, for all $x, y \in R$, by hypotheses

$$\theta(x^*)T(x) = S(x)\theta(x^*), \text{ for all } x \in R \quad (1)$$

If we substitute $x+y$ for x in (1), we get

$$\theta(x^*)T(y) + \theta(y^*)T(x) = S(x)\theta(y^*) + S(y)\theta(x^*), \text{ for all } x, y \in R. \quad (2)$$

Replace yz by y in (2) we arrive at

$$\theta(x^*)T(z)\theta(y^*) + \theta(z^*)\theta(y^*)T(x) = S(x)\theta(z^*)\theta(y^*) + \theta(z^*)S(y)\theta(x^*),$$

for all $x, y, z \in R$. (3)

Yields

$$(\theta(x^*)T(z) - S(x)\theta(z^*))\theta(y^*) = \theta(z^*)(S(y)\theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)),$$

for all $x, y, z \in R$. (4)

Putting $z = x$ in (4), we get

$$\theta(x^*)(S(y)\theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)) = 0, \text{ for all } x, y \in R. \quad (5)$$

Replace y by yz in (5), we get

$$\theta(x^*)\theta(z^*)(S(y)\theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)) = 0, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in R. \quad (6)$$

We have, therefore

$$\theta(x^*)R(S(y)\theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)) = 0, \text{ for all } x, y \in R. \quad (7)$$

If we substitute $x + w$ for x in (7), we get

$$(\theta(x^*) + \theta(w^*))R(S(y)\theta(x^*) + S(y)\theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) = 0,$$

for all $x, y, w \in R$.

Implies that

$$\begin{aligned} & \theta(w^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) + \theta(w^*) R (S(y) \theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)) + \\ & \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)) + \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) = 0, \\ & \text{for all } x, y, w \in R. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) + \theta(w^*) R (S(y) \theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)) = 0, \\ & \text{for all } x, y, w \in R. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Implies that

$$\begin{aligned} & \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) = -\theta(w^*) R (S(y) \theta(x^*) - \theta(y^*)T(x)), \\ & \text{for all } x, y, w \in R. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Right multiplication (10) by $R \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w))$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) R \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) = -\theta(w^*) R (S(y) \theta(x^*) - \\ & \theta(y^*)T(x)) R \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)), \text{ for all } x, y, w \in R. \end{aligned}$$

Using relation (7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) R \theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) = 0, \\ & \text{for all } x, y, w \in R. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

By the semiprimeness of R , we get

$$\theta(x^*) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) = 0, \text{ for all } x, y, w \in R. \quad (12)$$

Replace $\theta(x^*)$ by $(S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w))$ in (12), we get

$$(S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) R (S(y) \theta(w^*) - \theta(y^*)T(w)) = 0, \text{ for all } x, y, w \in R. \quad (13)$$

Again by the semiprimeness of R , we get

$$\theta(y^*)T(w) = S(y) \theta(w^*), \text{ for all } y, w \in R.$$

Lemma 3.7: Let R be $*$ -ring with an identity element. Then (T, S) is a double Jordan θ^* -centralizer if and only if T and S are of the form $T(x) = a \theta(x^*)$ and $S(x) = \theta(x^*) a$ for some fixed element $a \in R$, where θ is an automorphism of R .

Proof: Let (T, S) be a double Jordan θ^* -centralizer, then

$$T(x^2) = T(x) \theta(x^*) \text{ for all } x \in R. \quad (1)$$

$$S(x^2) = \theta(x^*) S(x) \text{ for all } x \in R. \quad (2)$$

$$\theta(x^*)T(x) = S(x) \theta(x^*) \text{ for all } x \in R \quad (3)$$

Replace x by $x + 1$ in (1), we get

$$T(x) = a \theta(x^*) \text{ for all } x \in R. \text{ Where } a = T(1)$$

Also, replace x by $x + 1$ in (2), we get

$$S(x) = \theta(x^*) b \text{ for all } x \in R. \text{ Where } b = S(1)$$

Now , setting $x = 1$ in (3) , we obtain $a = b$.

Thus , $T(x) = a \theta(x^*)$ and $S(x) = \theta(x^*) a$, for all $x \in R$.

To show the converse , assume that $T(x) = a \theta(x^*)$ and $S(x) = \theta(x^*) a$, then

$$T(x^2) = a (\theta(x^*))^2 = T(x) \theta(x^*) \text{ for all } x \in R .$$

Hence, T is a left Jordan θ^* - centralizer .

In similar way, we can show that S is a right Jordan θ^* - centralizer where $S(x) = \theta(x^*) a$, for all $x \in R$. Since $\theta(x^*)T(x) = \theta(x^*) a \theta(x^*) = S(x) \theta(x^*)$, therefore

(T,S) is a double Jordan θ^* - centralizer .

Lemma 3.8: Let R be $*$ - ring with an identity element , then $T : R \rightarrow R$ is a left (right) reverse θ^* - centralizer if and only if T is of the form $T(x) = a \theta(x^*)$ ($T(x) = \theta(x^*) a$) for some fixed element $a \in R$, where θ is an automorphism of R.

Proof: Let T be a left reverse θ^* - centralizer, then

$$T(xy) = T(y) \theta(x^*) , \text{ for all } x, y \in R .$$

Replace y by 1 we get

$$T(x) = a \theta(x^*) , \text{ for all } x \in R . \text{ Where } a = T(1)$$

$$\text{If } T(xy) = \theta(y^*)T(x), \text{ for all } x, y \in R$$

Replace x by 1 we get

$$T(y) = \theta(y^*) a , \text{ for all } y \in R . \text{ Where } a = T(1)$$

To show the converse , assume $T(x) = a \theta(x^*)$ for all $x \in R$. Then

$$T(xy) = a \theta((xy)^*) = a \theta(y^* x^*) = a \theta(y^*) \theta(x^*) = T(y) \theta(x^*) , \text{ for all } x, y \in R .$$

Hence T is a left reverse θ^* - centralizer , similar we can show T is right reverse

$$\theta^* \text{ - centralizer if } T(x) = a \theta(x^*) , \text{ for all } x \in R .$$

Theorem 3.9: Let R be $*$ - ring with an identity element , then every double Jordan θ^* - centralizer is a double reverse θ^* - centralizer , where θ is an automorphism of R .

Proof: Let (T,S) be a double Jordan θ^* - centralizer , then from Lemma (3.7) , we get T and S are of the form $T(x) = a \theta(x^*)$ and $S(x) = \theta(x^*) a$ for some fixed element $a \in R$, and from Lemma (3.8), we get T is a left reverse θ^* - centralizer, S is a right reverse θ^* - centralizer , and $\theta(x^*)T(y) = \theta(x^*) a \theta(y^*) = S(x) \theta(y^*)$, therefore (T,S) is a double reverse θ^* - centralizer

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